

CUBA - 2024

11TH TTP CONFERENCE

Cuba

<https://www.zooparaz.net/ttp11>

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM ABSTRACT BOOK

TTP Conference is one of the most important conventions in the world devoted to taxonomy and evolution of ticks and tick – borne pathogens, their ecology and epidemiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and strategies for their control including immunity and vaccines among others.

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11th Tick & Tick-borne Pathogen Conference

Cuba 2024

1st - 6th

September, 2024

Havana, Varadero, Cuba

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Oral presentations

Symposium Ecology and epidemiology of Ticks and
tick-borne Pathogens
Room La Corona, Meliá Cohiba

10:00-10:20

ZOONOTIC TICK-BORNE PATHOGENS IN SERBIA: WHAT WE KNOW AND WHAT WE DON'T KNOW?

Potkonjak Aleksandar¹, Savić Sara², Petrović Tamaš², Banović Pavle³, Ristanović Elizabeta⁴, Protić Đokić Vesna⁴, Pavlović Nevenka⁵, Kovačević Filipović Milica⁶, Jurišić Aleksandar⁷, Pustahija Tatjana⁸, Sević Siniša⁹, Poluga Jasmina¹⁰, Turkulov Vesna⁹

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In the past two decades, several research groups in major scientific, educational, health, veterinary and military institutions have intensively investigated the presence and distribution of zoonotic tick-borne pathogens in Serbia. These studies were carried out using molecular biology methods (conventional, real-time or microfluidic real-time PCR and partial sequencing) for tick pathogen investigation. It is important to point out that studies, apart from Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV), were only and exclusively related to bacteria and protozoa. Thus, the presence of the following pathogens was identified in different population of ticks and in different geographical locations of Serbia: *Borrelia burgdorferi* s.s., *B. afzelii*, *B. garinii*, *B. lusitaniae*, *B. valaisiana*, *B. miyamotoi*, *Rickettsia monacensis*, *R. raoultii*, *R. massiliae*, *R. helvetica*, *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*, *Neoehrlichia mikurensis*, *Babesia microti* and *B. venatorum*. In addition to the applied methods of molecular biology, the successful cultivation of *Borrelia* spp. was also established (eg. *Borrelia afzelii* in BSK-H medium with antibiotics).

In addition to the research done on ticks, serological analysis were carried out in sentinel population of animals (eg. seroreactivity in dogs has been proven for *Borrelia burgdorferi* sensu lato complex, *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* and *Rickettsia conorii*). Some diseases from this group have also been registered in humans by infectious disease specialists in collaboration with microbiologists and epidemiologists (different clinical stages of Lyme borreliosis, which is expected because Serbia is an endemic area; and also rare cases of TBEV infection or TBEV seropositivity).

The causative agent of tick-borne encephalitis is relatively poorly investigated and there is a limited number of studies in Serbia. It was believed that TBEV was absent from the country, after the first registration in 1972. However, in recent years, the presence of TBEV has been confirmed in ticks (by PCR and partial sequencing) as well as in animals and humans (by serology tests).

Based on the above, it is evident that research on other viruses in ticks has not been carried out in Serbia so far, although more viruses with public health significance circulate in ticks such as the following ones: Omsk hemorrhagic fever virus and Kyasanur forest disease virus from genus *Orthoflavivirus*; Crimean–Congo hemorrhagic fever virus from g. *Orthonairovirus*; Bandavirus bhanjanagarensis (previous Bhanja virus) from g. *Bandavirus*; Thogotovirus thogotoense (previous Thogoto virus) and Thogotovirus dhoriense (previous Dhori virus) from g. *Thogotovirus*; and Eyach coltivirus (previous Eyach virus) from g. *Coltivirus*. Also, novel tick-associated viruses with unknown zoonotic potential have to be taken into consideration.

Therefore, we point out that in Serbia, the epidemiological situation regarding tick-borne viruses is not investigated extensively and the future research on tick-borne pathogens must highlight of viruses in ticks. The most useful data could be obtained with a metagenomic approach.

Key words: Tick-borne pathogens, zoonotic, viruses, bacteria, protozoa, Serbia